

USING DIGITAL LEARNING MEDIA AND LITERACY TO IMPROVE DESCRIPTIVE TEXT WRITING SKILLS OF JUNIOR HIGH SCHOOL STUDENTS

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Abstract

Current descriptive text writing instruction requires innovations in digital learning media to match the digital era. Students face challenges in improving their descriptive text writing skills, with proficiency levels often low. Implementing digital learning media and literacy is crucial to addressing this issue. This study investigates the impact of combining digital learning media and writing literacy on students' descriptive text writing skills using a true experimental quantitative approach. Data were collected from descriptive text writing tests at three junior high schools, focusing on title accuracy, identification, content description, language use, and conclusion. The study underwent validation, reliability, and prerequisite tests to ensure data normality and homogeneity. Descriptive and inferential statistical analyses, including t-tests and F-tests, were conducted. Results showed that the combined use of digital learning media and literacy significantly improved descriptive text writing skills. Hypothesis analysis revealed a t-value of 3.868 with a significance level of 0.000, indicating that the difference between the digital media group and the control group was significant. Thus, the combined application of digital learning media and literacy effectively enhances junior high school students' descriptive text writing skills.

Keywords: Descriptive Text, Digital Media, Literacy, Media, Writing Skills.

1. INTRODUCTION

Writing skills play an essential role and need continuous refinement. Good writing skills allow students to convey information clearly and understandably. These skills are crucial in academic contexts, various professions, and daily life. In the context of Indonesian language learning at the junior high school level, the ability to write descriptive texts is a key competency that students must master. This skill focuses on the ability to describe objects, places, or events clearly. Success in writing descriptive texts requires a deep understanding of the topic and good language mastery, necessitating regular and continuous practice for clarity and comprehension.

The teaching of descriptive text writing skills to students remains inadequate. Students struggle to develop main ideas for paragraphs and differentiate between narrative and descriptive writing (Jayanti & Fachrurazi, 2020). Low performance in descriptive writing is also due to a lack of motivation and support from learning media (Mirnawati & Firman, 2019). This skill is challenging for students as it involves observing, organizing ideas, and conveying information clearly (Collins, Brown, & Newman, 2018; Fareed et al., 2016). Students face several challenges in learning to write descriptive texts, including difficulty in word choice and effective sentence construction (Lutfiah, Rukayah, & Kamsiyati, 2021). Additionally, students struggle with idea development, vocabulary mastery, theme selection, appropriate language style use, and imagination in descriptive writing due to simplistic teaching approaches (Dewi & Yuliana, 2018). Most students have not yet achieved the Minimum Completeness Criteria in writing descriptive texts (Kusumantara et al., 2017). Addressing this issue is crucial as descriptive text writing is a vital language skill.

To overcome these challenges, innovations in engaging and interactive learning media are necessary, particularly with digital media. Students need to be introduced to learning innovations that keep pace with the times, allowing for active participation in the learning process. This can enhance their understanding and adaptation to the digital context.

In the digital era, many students demonstrate proficiency in writing visual descriptions with descriptive words. This skill requires precise information delivery and creates a sensory experience through descriptive writing. It reflects significant developments in digital communication skills in today's information age, showing students' adaptation to technology and their ability to use digital media to express ideas, experiences, and views effectively to a global audience.

Implementing digital learning media is a crucial breakthrough in improving students' descriptive text writing skills (Asri, Kurniawan, & Cahyani, 2023). Digital media brings educational innovations that support the learning process in schools by offering greater interactivity and creating a more comprehensive and relevant learning experience for students.

Using digital media such as Sketchbook and IbisPaint X to enhance descriptive writing skills based on visual media is a key focus. Evaluation measures their success in literacy writing based on visual media and descriptive text writing skills in the context of Indonesian literacy in junior high schools. This process integrates visual creativity with writing skills, enhancing personal expression and the ability to communicate ideas effectively through descriptive texts.

Sketchbook and IbisPaint X are two digital applications that play an important role in improving students' visual-based descriptive writing skills. Sketchbook allows users to create high-detail and precision digital sketches, helping students visually describe objects, places, or events clearly. IbisPaint X provides tools for digital drawing and coloring with various effects and features, enabling students to produce refined and varied digital art. These applications help students develop the ability to depict important details and enrich their ability to write vivid and imaginative descriptive texts.

The use of Sketchbook and IbisPaint X in learning also brings benefits by integrating visual creativity with writing skills effectively. Students can produce more in-depth and interesting descriptions using shading techniques, color usage, and other visual effects provided by these applications. This learning process can improve the visual quality of descriptions and teach students to communicate ideas and experiences more clearly and expressively. Thus, using digital media (Sketchbook and IbisPaint X) not only provides an interactive and enjoyable learning experience but also supports the development of Indonesian language literacy skills in junior high schools.

Digital media usage is expected to improve students' descriptive text writing skills. Through these media, students can combine writing skills with visual creativity, making their writing more interesting and varied. Visual media usage can also increase students' learning motivation through an interactive and enjoyable approach. The flexibility and accessibility of digital media allow for more independent learning accessible anywhere, thus enhancing the learning process's effectiveness.

Integrating digital media with writing literacy in schools is an essential part of the educational curriculum. Literacy helps students understand and apply the knowledge gained during learning and plays a role in character formation both at school and at home (Setiawan, Aji, & Aziz, 2019). Implementing literacy is key to enhancing students' descriptive text writing skills. Through literacy, students can also develop a deep understanding and practical skills in descriptive writing literacy. Low literacy levels in Indonesia, as highlighted by Nudiati & Sudiapermana (2020), present a serious challenge. Akbar's (2020) research shows that although students understand the importance of reading, few actively engage in it. This phenomenon reflects a gap between understanding the importance of literacy and its implementation in daily life. The impact of low literacy is not only limited to mastery of science and technology but also potentially affects the quality of human resources in the future. Therefore, improving literacy is crucial to ensure sustainable and quality development in Indonesia.

Implementing literacy in writing descriptive texts includes aspects such as proper word choice and logical idea arrangement (Anindya, Malawi, & Jatmikawati, 2023). Reading examples of descriptive texts is essential to understand effective writing structures and styles (Alawia, 2019). Feedback from educators and peers is also vital in improving the quality of descriptive writing (Hartati, 2021). Holistically, literacy implementation plays a role in developing students' descriptive text writing skills to a higher level.

Previous research by Zainuddin et al. (2022) examined the use of digital learning media in the development of writing literacy. This study provides a foundation for understanding the effectiveness of digital technology in enriching the writing learning process in educational settings. Meanwhile, research by Bakri and Hakim (2022) highlights the importance of combining digital media use and literacy application in enhancing students' writing skills. The findings from these studies provide a strong theoretical basis for exploring the positive impact of integrating digital learning media and literacy in the context of current education and writing instruction.

Further research conducted by Vitriani et al. (2022) indicates that digital media is highly effective in the context of writing instruction. Digital media facilitate students' ability to imagine better, providing a broader creative space in the writing process. Similar findings were revealed by Qulub and Renhoat (2020), who highlighted that the use of digital media successfully attracted students' interest and significantly improved their ability to write descriptive texts. Another study by Harefa et al. (2023) also confirmed that digital media play an important role in enhancing students' descriptive text writing skills, providing additional evidence of the positive benefits of integrating technology into writing education.

Despite the growing body of research on the integration of digital learning media and literacy in enhancing students' writing skills, there remains a significant gap in understanding the specific impact of such interventions on descriptive text writing skills at the junior high school level. Previous studies by Zainuddin et al. (2022) and Bakri and Hakim (2022) have established the general effectiveness of digital media in improving writing literacy, yet they have not thoroughly explored how these tools can address the unique challenges faced by students in descriptive writing, such as idea development, vocabulary mastery, and effective sentence construction. Additionally, while Vitriani et al. (2022) and Qulub and Renhoat (2020) demonstrated the potential of digital media to foster creativity and engagement in writing, they did not specifically examine the use of applications like Sketchbook and IbisPaint X in enhancing visual-based descriptive writing skills. This study aims to fill this gap by investigating the combined effect of digital learning media and literacy on students' ability to write descriptive texts, offering a novel approach that integrates visual creativity with writing proficiency to provide a more engaging and effective learning experience.

Integrating digital media with literacy allows students to effectively combine writing skills with drawing abilities. With the capability to produce attractive visuals, digital media can clarify and enrich ideas in writing. The flexibility of using digital media also provides opportunities for students to learn independently. For educators, it enables providing in-depth and detailed feedback directly on students' visual work, thereby strengthening students' overall literacy skills.

Education in the digital era demands innovation in learning development, especially in improving students' writing skills through the integration of digital learning media such as Sketchbook and IbisPaint X, and the application of literacy in the writing context. The purpose of this research is to explore the extent to which the combination of digital learning media and writing literacy significantly affects students' descriptive text writing skills. This is the core issue that the research aims to address.

2. METHOD

This study employs a true experimental method to test the cause-and-effect relationship between the variables under investigation (Agustianti, 2022). A quantitative approach with a true experimental method was used to randomly assign participants to experimental groups (receiving treatment) and control groups (not receiving treatment) (Simanullang, 2022). The research population consists of seventh-grade students from State Junior High Schools in

Jakarta, selected using Area Simple Random Sampling technique with allocations for both the experimental and control groups from three schools. Data collection was conducted through descriptive text writing tests, with indicators modified from theories by Alderson (2009), Wimmer (2013), Imawati (2017), Adawiyah (2019), Lestari (2018), Anriani (2019), Suhardiana (2019), and guidelines from the Indonesian Language Teacher's Book for Junior High School/Madrasah Tsanawiyah Class VII (2023). These indicators include title accuracy, identification, content description, language use, and conclusion.

Before conducting the research, validation and reliability tests were performed by expert panels, along with prerequisite tests to ensure data normality and homogeneity. After confirming data normality, descriptive statistical analysis and inferential analysis were carried out. Hypothesis testing employed statistical calculations for mean difference tests (t-tests and F-tests).

3. RESULT

Pengolahan data dari penelitian ini melibatkan evaluasi kemampuan menulis teks Data processing in this study involved evaluating the descriptive text writing abilities of seventh-grade students from three state junior high schools in Jakarta. SMPN 19 and SMPN 115 served as the experimental groups using digital media Sketchbook and IbisPaint X, while SMPN 182 acted as the control group using conventional media. The evaluation was conducted using pre-tests and post-tests to measure the impact of the learning media intervention on students' writing abilities.

Descriptive Statistical Analysis

Table 1: Description of Pre-test and Post-test Scores

Data Experimental and Control Groups

Statistics	Pre-Test Eks 1	Post-Test Eks 1	Pre-Test Eks 2	Post-Test Eks 2	Pre-Test Control	Post-Test Control
Number of Respondents	288	288	288	288	288	288
Number of Classes	8	8	8	8	8	8
Mean	72.23	81.51	76.22	80.34	73.33	77.21
Median	74.00	81.00	78.00	80.50	74.00	77.00
Std. Deviation	7.122	3.833	6.044	3.416	3.942	3.122
Variance	50.723	14.690	36.536	11.668	15.538	9.747
Range	32	16	31	15	26	14
Minimum	51	73	55	73	55	70
Maximum	83	89	86	88	81	84

Table 1 presents the Pre-Test and Post-Test data for three groups: Experimental 1, Experimental 2, and Control. Experimental 1 has a Pre-Test average of 72.23 and a Post-Test average of 81.51, showing the highest increase (9.28). Experimental 2 shows a Pre-Test average of 76.22 and a Post-Test average of 80.34, with an increase of (4.12). The Control group has a Pre-Test average of 73.33 and a Post-Test average of 77.21, with the lowest increase (3.88). This data provides an overview of the different effects of the intervention on students' abilities and the

relevance of using digital media and literacy in improving descriptive text writing skills. The data indicates that students in Experimental Group 1 experienced a significant improvement in descriptive text writing skills from Pre-Test to Post-Test, with the highest scores. This illustrates the success of the digital learning media (Sketchbook) implemented in this group. These findings provide a strong basis for appreciating the effectiveness of such digital learning media in enhancing students' descriptive writing abilities compared to the control group. The values can be illustrated through the following histogram.

Figure 1: Histogram of Pre-Test and Post-Test Scores in Experimental and Control Groups for Descriptive Text Writing Skills

Prerequisite Test

Normality Test

The results of the normality test can be explained in the table below.

Table 2: Normality Test Results

No.	Class	Asymp. Sig. Kolmogorov-Smirnov ^a	Asymp. Sig. Shapiro-Wilk	Note
1.	Pre-Test Experiment 1	0.200	0.348	Normal
2.	Post-Test Experiment 1	0.200	0.344	Normal
3.	Pre-Test Experiment 2	0.100	0.271	Normal
4.	Post-Test Eksperimen 2	0.100	0.339	Normal
5.	Pre-Test Control	0.200	0.294	Normal
6.	Post-Test Control	0.130	0.351	Normal

The normality test results in the table above, using Kolmogorov-Smirnov and Shapiro-Wilk tests, indicate that all distributions are normal. All groups show p-values (Asymp.Sig.) greater than 0.05 in both tests for each group, indicating that the assumption of normality is met.

Homogeneity Test

In this study, the homogeneity test was conducted using Analysis of Variance (ANOVA). The importance of the homogeneity test in ANOVA lies in the assumption that the variance of the data in each group must be uniform. Ensuring homogeneity of variance is crucial because ANOVA results based on this assumption are more reliable and their interpretation is more valid.

Table 3: Homogeneity Test

ANOVA					
Writing Descriptive Texts					
	Sum of Squares	df	Mean Square	F	Sig.
Between Groups	2849.877	2	1424.939	118.400	0.314
Within Groups	10362.122	861	12.035		
Total	13211.999	863			

The homogeneity test showed that the variances among the groups (Experimental 1, Experimental 2, and Control) are homogeneous, with a significance value (Sig.) of 0.314, which is greater than 0.05. This means there is no significant difference in variances among the groups in their descriptive text writing abilities, thus meeting the homogeneity of variance assumption for ANOVA.

Hypothesis Testing

Table 4: Hypothesis Testing

		Independent Samples Test								
		Levene's Test for Equality of Variances		t-test for Equality of Means						
		F	Sig.	t	df	Sig. (2-tailed)	Mean Difference	Std. Error Difference	95% Confidence Interval of the Difference	
Writing Descriptive Texts	Equal variances assumed	6.222	.013	3.868	574	.000	1.170	.303	.576	1.764
	Equal variances not assumed			3.868	566.552	.000	1.170	.303	.576	1.764

Based on the hypothesis testing table above, it can be concluded that there is a significant influence of the combined use of digital learning media (Sketchbook and IbisPaint X) and literacy application on the ability to write descriptive texts. This is indicated by a significant t-value (t = 3.868) with a p-value (Sig. 2-tailed) of 0.000, which is much smaller than 0.05. This means that the difference in mean scores between the two groups in descriptive text writing ability is not due to chance and there is indeed a significant effect between the tested variables.

There is a clear difference in the average Post-Test scores of descriptive text writing skills between the experimental groups and the control group. Experimental Group 1 has an average Post-Test score of 81.51, Experimental Group 2 has an average Post-Test score of 80.34, and

the control group (SMPN 182 Jakarta) has an average Post-Test score of 77.21. These results show that both experimental groups, those using Sketchbook digital learning media (Experimental 1) and IbisPaint X (Experimental 2), have higher average scores compared to the control group.

4. DISCUSSIONS

The use of digital learning media (Sketchbook and IbisPaint X) and literacy in teaching descriptive text writing skills to seventh-grade students demonstrates a systematic approach. The learning was applied to experimental and control groups, beginning with a Pre-Test to measure students' initial understanding. In the experimental groups, three stages of treatment involving digital media and literacy were conducted. The first stage introduced the two digital media as tools to develop the ability to convey ideas more clearly and imaginatively.

In the second stage, the focus was on teaching the techniques of writing descriptive texts in depth. Students learned the key aspects of writing descriptive texts through indicators developed based on related theories and research, such as title accuracy, identification ability, dense content description, appropriate language use, and effective closure (Alderson, 2009; Wimmer, 2013; Imawati, 2017; Adawiyah, 2019; Lestari, 2018; Anriani, 2019; Suhardiana, 2019). In the third stage, students actively practiced the knowledge and skills they had learned. They were given the opportunity to develop descriptive writing skills independently with teacher guidance (Zahro, 2017). This process allowed students to explore creativity using digital media while enhancing their ability to organize and convey ideas in a structured manner. Teachers helped reinforce understanding, internalize, and apply writing skills more effectively in real contexts. In practice, teachers ensured that students had a strong understanding of digital literacy before using digital media in learning. Teachers conducted specific training according to the needs of the experimental groups. They also guided students to create sketches and link these images to the descriptive texts they wrote. This process aligns with guidelines from Sangvanich & Chinokul (2018), where digital media is used to create sketches based on topics linked to the written descriptive texts.

In practice, there was variation in students' abilities to master the use of digital media. Some students adapted quickly to the technology, while others had limited experience or access. Teachers played a crucial role in providing guidance and motivation to help each student overcome these challenges, ensuring they remained engaged in the learning process. The next step was to create collaboration among students. This process involved activities that required students to share their sketches and descriptions (Cornwall & Park, 2022; Moate et al., 2019). Teachers facilitated this collaborative process to provide constructive feedback and enable students to learn from their classmates' work. Collaboration is an integral part of developing students' social and professional skills. In the final stage, a Post-Test evaluation was conducted where students were asked to write descriptive texts using the digital media and literacy they had learned. This evaluation measured the improvement in descriptive text writing skills after a series of treatments. The Post-Test results provided a deeper insight into the effectiveness of using digital media and literacy in enhancing middle school students' descriptive text writing

skills. As a final step, teachers facilitated a reflection session with students. This reflection is crucial as a key element in developing descriptive writing skills using digital media (Moate et al., 2019; Power, 2018). By implementing all these steps, teachers ensured that the use of digital media and literacy effectively supported the learning of descriptive text writing and helped students develop holistically in this digital era. In the control group, conventional media, such as print media and images, were used. Teachers began by providing a clear understanding to students on how to use these media to note and develop ideas (Croteau & Hoynes, 2013). An in-depth explanation of descriptive text writing skills was also provided, including various relevant indicators, similar to those given to the experimental groups. Teachers detailed the usefulness of print media and images in the context of writing descriptive texts. They illustrated how images could help organize ideas and describe them in a structured manner. Subsequently, teachers gave relevant exercises to students in the control group, such as writing descriptions based on specific images or illustrations.

During the exercises, teachers directed students to focus on details and appropriate language use in the descriptive texts they created. Teachers assigned challenging tasks to develop descriptions based on images or illustrations, encouraging the application of learned techniques. Pre-Test and Post-Test evaluations were also conducted to assess students' progress and provide constructive feedback. Teachers also helped students give feedback to each other, creating a collaborative learning environment through interaction and discussion. This process allowed students to learn from each other and improve their writing based on received input.

By applying basic principles of descriptive text writing skills effectively, teachers ensured that students in the control group gained maximum benefits from the use of print media and images. Teacher support in guiding the learning process helped students develop strong descriptive writing skills, even without digital media like the experimental groups. This process demonstrated that conventional media remain effective in enhancing students' descriptive text writing skills with adequate guidance and practice. The simultaneous use of digital learning media (Sketchbook and IbisPaint X) and literacy showed a significant impact on descriptive text writing skills. Hypothesis testing results showed a t-value of 3.868 with a significance level (Sig. 2-tailed) of 0.000, far below 0.05. This indicates that the difference between the groups using digital media and the control group is highly significant and not due to chance. Thus, it can be concluded that students using digital learning media and literacy showed better improvement in descriptive text writing skills compared to students in the control group using conventional media (print/images). This research finding indicates that middle school students' descriptive text writing skills are more effectively enhanced using digital learning media than conventional media. Therefore, the integration of digital technology in learning, combined with literacy strategies, has been proven to have a significant positive impact on students' descriptive text writing skills. The simultaneous use of digital learning media and literacy strategies significantly impacts middle school students' descriptive writing skills. Through digital media, students can develop visual creativity more expressively and dynamically, producing more detailed and clear descriptive texts. The combined use of digital learning media and literacy has a positive and significant impact on descriptive writing skills. These digital learning media provide students with a platform to sketch, draw, and color creatively and interactively

(Marshall, 2024; Cornwall & Park, 2022). The diverse features of these media allow the creation of detailed and interesting images, supporting the effective development of descriptive text writing skills. The use of digital media plays a vital role in developing students' visual literacy (David, 2023; Oktaviani, 2022; Power, 2018). Through these applications, students can learn creative drawing techniques and integrate images, diagrams, or mind maps as integral elements of the descriptive writing process. This process can enhance students' ability to arrange words effectively and make it easier to convey information visually and attractively (Genlott & Grönlund, 2013).

Students can express their creativity with the digital media provided on each platform (Partridge, 2021; Kuschnir, 2016). This interactivity encourages collaborative learning, where students can share their work, give and receive feedback, and collaborate on creative projects. This experience makes learning more enjoyable for students and enhances their observation and description skills. Through the use of digital media, students can continually refine and reflect on their writing. The application of literacy in the context of digital media introduces students to a deep understanding of effective writing structure and appropriate language use (Baxter, 2019; Power, 2018). Similar findings were also found by Qulub and Renhoat (2020), highlighting that digital media stimulate students' interest and substantially improve their ability to compose clear and in-depth descriptive texts. Thus, the use of digital media helps students express details in descriptive texts through appropriate structure and language, creating innovative and effective learning. The combination of digital media use and literacy application opens up opportunities for students to develop descriptive writing skills effectively. Students are encouraged to carefully observe images, identify every important detail, and express them in clear and concise descriptions. This process not only teaches students to be detailed information sources but also trains them to organize their observations and write them in a structured format (Baxter, 2019).

Careful observation of image details helps students hone their observational skills (Hockey & Forsey, 2020), making them more attentive to small but important aspects of writing descriptive texts. Additionally, this exercise also trains students to organize their thoughts logically and systematically, resulting in more coherent and easily understandable descriptions (Bean & Melzer, 2021; Graham, 2019; Williams, 2014). With consistent practice, students will become more skilled in conveying ideas in a detailed and systematic manner (Collins, Brown, & Newman, 2018; Kennedy, 2016), enabling them to compose informative and engaging descriptions. The combination of digital media and literacy effectively enhances students' descriptive text writing skills creatively and productively. Collaboration and discussion about images in learning provide students with diverse learning experiences. This sharing process offers new insights and inspires fresh ideas in students' creativity. These findings are consistent with those of Pakaya & Hakeu (2023), which highlight that collaboration can enhance students' artistic and interpretive abilities and strengthen their communication and social interaction skills. Research by Ramdhani (2023) also confirms that collaboration can hone artistic and interpretive skills and improve students' communication and social interaction abilities. This collaborative process not only reinforces the understanding that communication is an interactive process involving the exchange of ideas and views from various parties (Servaes,

2022; McGrath, 2014; Castells, 2013) but also teaches students to listen to and appreciate others' opinions. The interpersonal skills gained from this process are highly valuable in both academic contexts and everyday life. The use of digital media allows students to transform their ideas into accurate visual representations that align with their concepts. This broadens students' ability to express ideas creatively, as observed in Naimar's (2022) research. These findings are also relevant to the research by Harefa et al. (2023), where digital media not only develop students' visual abilities, but also enhance their critical and analytical thinking skills. The interactive tools provided by digital media make the learning process more engaging and effective. In terms of literacy application, it helps students develop a deep understanding of the topics they describe through digital media. This research reinforces the findings of Kong (2014), which suggest that literacy not only enriches students' knowledge but also improves their ability to compose more informative and comprehensive descriptions (August & Shanahan, 2017; Gee, 2015). Consequently, students can communicate their ideas more clearly and effectively while expanding their understanding of the subject matter.

The application of literacy in learning emphasizes the technical aspects of writing and the ability of students to respond to texts critically to produce original and substantial writing. Literacy aids students in formulating precise words and enriching details in descriptive texts (Gee, 2015). These findings align with the research by Yulistio & Fhitri (2019), highlighting the importance of developing a comprehensive writing culture and encouraging students' ability to generate critical and creative ideas. This provides a strong foundation for developing academic literacy and preparing students to face challenges and opportunities in life.

This study confirms that integrating digital media with literacy application in teaching descriptive text writing skills can significantly enhance students' ability to express their ideas more effectively. Students feel that this technology not only provides a more interactive and enjoyable learning experience but also offers flexibility in access and usage, supporting independent learning. The implications of this combination have a wide-ranging impact on students. This combination provides a solid foundation for students' descriptive text writing and communication skills in various aspects of life. It is highly relevant in academic contexts and prepares students to become individuals capable of effective communication and critical thinking in an increasingly digital society. In implementing digital media and literacy application in teaching descriptive text writing skills, students may face several challenges that need to be addressed. Limited access to technology and infrastructure can hinder students' opportunities to optimally use digital media devices in the learning process (Scheerder, Van Deursen, & Van Dijk, 2017; Widayanti, 2015; Madianou & Miller, 2013). This requires additional efforts from schools to ensure that all students have equal access to the necessary software and hardware.

The technical complexity of digital media can be a barrier for students who are not yet familiar with this technology (Cabueños et al., 2024; Yuktirat, Sindhuphak, & Kiddee, 2018). Students need additional time to understand the various tools and features within the applications, which can disrupt their focus on the descriptive text writing process. Teacher readiness and skills are also crucial factors in the successful implementation of digital media and literacy in learning

(Daulay, 2021). Competent teachers who are proficient in using these digital media are needed to effectively convey and train students to enhance their descriptive text writing skills. Evaluating students' progress in using digital media and literacy is also a unique challenge (Hidayanti, 2021; Fatimah, Abdulkarim, & Iswandi, 2020). Besides observing the visual work of students, teachers also need to assess students' ability to convey ideas effectively in writing. This requires clear and consistent indicators or assessment rubrics, aligned with the existing curriculum. With a deep awareness of the existing constraints, schools and teachers can collaborate to implement effective strategies in leveraging the potential of digital media and literacy in learning. This not only provides valuable learning experiences for students but also yields positive results in developing critical, creative, and relevant communication skills in the current digital era. Optimal strategy implementation will help students face challenges and opportunities in an increasingly digital world with greater readiness and confidence.

5. CONCLUSION

The use of digital learning media such as Sketchbook and IbisPaint X, combined with literacy, has proven effective in enhancing the descriptive text writing abilities of junior high school students. The research results indicate that the experimental groups using these digital media showed a significantly greater improvement in writing skills compared to the control group using conventional media. Digital media provide a platform for students to express ideas more creatively and structurally, while literacy helps them understand and apply effective writing techniques. Despite challenges related to technological access and technical understanding, this study confirms that the integration of digital media and literacy can enhance students' descriptive writing skills, providing a strong foundation for the development of better communication skills in the digital era. Furthermore, the integration of these tools encourages students to engage more deeply with the learning material, fostering both individual and collaborative learning experiences. By utilizing digital media, students can explore and develop their creativity in ways that traditional media may not support, ultimately leading to a more dynamic and effective educational experience.

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